

An Experimental Study of Matrix Acidizing in Sandstone Reservoirs

ALI S. ALNETAIFI

**Petroleum and Natural Gas Engineering Department,
College of Engineering,
King Saud University, Riyadh, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia
E-mail: aalnetaiifi@gmail.com**

ABSTRACT

Acidizing job has been considered a vital process to treat and stimulate permeability of oil reservoirs since permeability reduction, where is located around wellbore of hydrocarbon zone, can be occurred using drilling mud. In this paper, it has been studied the performance of acidizing job as one-step in fractured and unfractured cores, that have damaged and undamaged using drilling mud, has been investigated under high pressure and temperature. All sandstone cores are saturated with Saudi formation water, and ammonium chloride solution is then injected as pre-treatment stage for cleaning core from any chemical minerals that can be occurred precipitation phenomena. The main organic acid mixture (2wt% hydrofluoric acid and 15wt% acetic acid) is then injected. The post-treatment stage is done by injecting ammonium chloride solution to remove out spent acid, and keep the wettability of formation. Finally, drainage and imbibition processes are implemented in all cores using n-decane as oleic phase and SFW as aqueous phase. In conclusion, the porosities and permeabilities of unfractured cores after treatment process are enhanced. On the other hand, the permeability of 45 degree fractured core cannot return to the original permeability since it is visually observed that acid bypasses the damaged area through fracture.

Keywords: Acidizing, Recovery Factor, Permeability Treatment Factor, Drilling Mud, Fractured and unfractured Cores

INTRODUCTION

It has been well known that the main purpose of acidizing job is to create channels around wellbore and to clean porous media from any damages that can be occurred using drilling mud in order to enhance the permeability of formation as well as the well productivity. Inorganic mud acid mixture, which is composed of hydrofluoric and hydrochloric acids, has been utilized to implement acidizing job practically. These can react and dissolve minerals such as silica, feldspar and carbonates, and the permeability can be then enhancement, however, formation damage can be occurred due to precipitations phenomena as reported Thomas et al. (2001) Al-Dahlan et al. (2001).

According to world energy demand and consumption (Aboud et al., 2007), well stimulation is a vital parameter for low productivity wells to fulfil the mentioned demand in the world. The new acidizing technique for sandstone reservoir, which relates to acid mixture, is practically required especially in reservoir temperature as well as pressure. Since inorganic acid mixture under reservoir condition causes fast rate of reaction, as a result, the acidizing process is inefficiency (Al-Harthy et al., 2009). Yang et al., 2012 and Al-Harbi et al., (2013) were studied the effectiveness of sandstone acidizing using organic mud acid mixture. For implementing organic mud acids in the field, the mixture of 5wt% acetic acid and 5wt% hydrochloric acid was injected in sandstone field where is located in

kingdom of Saudi Arabia, and this acidizing job was for stimulating water supply wells (Nasr-El-Din et al., 1997; and Hashem and Hopkins, 1999). Furthermore, formic acids can use in the well stimulation at concentration up to 9 wt%. In addition, organic acids can utilize with hydrochloric acid as iron control agents, and corrosion inhibitors

The main objective of this paper is experimentally investigated a new successful technique for matrix acidizing of sandstone reservoir using organic mud acid mixture which is composed of 2wt% hydrofluoric acid and 15wt% acetic acid. This technique can be then applied on several scenarios such as damaged and undamaged cores, and fractured and unfractured cores. Finally, all scenarios are evaluated by measuring porosity and permeability before and after treatment, furthermore, the drainage and imbibition processes are done in all cores to measure its permeabilities as well as recoveries at 1000 psi and 140°F

The Concepts of Chemical Reactions Of Used Fluids

There have been several organic acids such as formic, citric and acetic acids, and those are called carboxylic acids, furthermore, all of them are known weak acids comparing with the hydrochloric or sulphuric acids. Most organic acids have been complicated to measure their corrosion rates due to impurities effect, and these acids can be naturally found from gas condensate wells. However, the acetic acid has been commonly injected to retain acidity and eliminate any solids precipitations, and it has been significant implication especially for the integrity of metals such as vessels and pipes, and it is environmentally friendly. The viscosity, density and molecular weight of acetic acid are 2 cp, 1.05 gm/cc and 60 respectively. In addition, the acetic acid can react with aqueous solution, which is composed of sodium chloride, and its result is hydrochloric acid. It is concluded that the increase of the acetic acid concentration in mud acid with chloride ion existence at high temperature perhaps results the highest concentration of hydrochloric acid, and this leads to increase the corrosion rate.

The Saudi formation water "SFW" is composed of 5.89wt% sodium chloride, 2.24wt% calcium chloride and 0.15wt% magnesium chloride, its density and viscosity values are 1.065 gm/cc and 1.3 cp. As observe in the salt percentages in SFW, the possibility of corrosion rate accelerates. Thus, the hydrochloric acid is not recommend to use as pre-flush stage since hydrochloric acid increases the corrosion rate instantaneously. Hence, ammonium chloride is candidate and used instead of hydrochloric acid since the ammonium chloride is mildly acidic and, the PH of 5wt% ammonium chloride solution can be 5.5, moreover, the aspect of ammonium chloride is a compatible solution with formation as well as acids. To sum up, it is injected 5wt% of ammonium chloride as pre-treatment stage, and main treatment acids mixture is a combination of 5wt% ammonium chloride and organic mud acid "15wt% HAc and 2wt% HF" as describe in the equations:

As observe in Equations (1) and (2), results of all chemical reactions produce hydrochloric acids so the hydrochloric acid cannot be used to implement the objective of this study for decreasing corrosion rate especially at high pressure and temperature.

This paper is addressed the new mechanism of matrix treatment in both fractured and unfractured sandstone formations. The mechanism is relevant to implement the treatment process as one-step using the organic mud acids mixture which can be compatible with the formation and fluids in order to lead achievable and successful treatments. This mechanism can preserve and maintain the flooding unit from corrosion issue, and economically implement rapidly without consuming time comparing with the traditional treatment.

Laboratory Apparatus and Procedures

Equipment and Materials

Several Berea sandstone cores are conducted to do the acidizing job in this study, and those are composed of high percentage of quartz and low percentage of clay. Consequently, the acidizing process can be more efficient rather than hydraulic fracturing since its permeabilities are actually moderate. For fractured sandstone core, the electrical saw is used to create channel "2mm width and 2mm depth" upon the core with 45 degree to examine the acidizing job in fractured sandstone core.

Balance, pycnometer, viscometer, vacuum desiccator and pump, accumulators, temperature tapes and controller, injection pump, confining pump, Hassler core holder and back pressure regulator are used to build up vacuum and flooding units, and all rock and fluid properties can be experimentally measured. Graduated plastic tubes, containers and flasks are recommend to use in the acidizing stage to eliminate any adsorption effects with acids. Saudi formation water “SFW” is prepared to mimic the Saudi reservoir, and it is composed of 5.89wt% sodium chloride, 2.24wt% calcium chloride and 0.15wt% magnesium chloride. Drilling mud, which is composed of bentonite and its density 1.17 gm/cc, is prepared to inject inside core, and represent a real issue case. Solution of 5wt% ammonium chloride “NH₄Cl” is prepared for implementing pre- and post-treatment stages. Finally, 15wt% acetic and 2wt% hydrofluoric acids are mixed with 5wt% ammonium chloride solution to apply main treatment stage. n-Decane is considered to be an oleic phase to investigate oil phase flow after treatment stage.

Experimental Procedures

The acidizing experiments using organic mud acids mixture are conducted, and there are several stages of measurements that have been done in this study. The homogenous and fractured Berea sandstone cores are firstly dried and warmed for several hours using oven, the weights of all cores are then balanced to find the dry weight for all cores. After that, all cores are put in a vacuum desiccator as shown in the Figure 1, and vacuum pump is then worked to evacuate air from the pores of all cores. Then, all cores are saturated with Saudi formation water to simulate the real reservoir. After all cores saturation with SFW, each core is balanced to determine saturated weight, and then calculate its pore volume (weight difference over SWF density), and the bulk volume of each core can be determined using cylindrical volume

Figure 1: Schematic of Vacuum and Saturation Unit.

Finally, porosity of each core can be calculated, and this porosity is called pre-porosity which is before the treatment process. Moreover, in the fractured sandstone core, it contains two porosities which relate to core sample storage and fracture storage.

Experiments are performed using both homogeneous and fractured cores that are approximately 3.6 inches long and 1.5 inches diameter. The pore pressure and temperature of all experiments are 1000 psi and 140°F respectively. To demonstrate its pressure and temperature conditions, the back pressure regulator, temperature tapes and controller are used, in addition, the pressure differences between the

pore and overburden pressure are almost 300 psi. Using Teledyne ISCO Pump, the injection rate of SFW, main treatment, drainage and imbibition processes is 2 cc/min except the injection rate of pre-treatment and post-treatment stages using ammonium chloride solution is 5 cc/min due to clean porous media from magnesium, sodium and calcium precipitations, and the remaining organic mud acid. To record inlet and outlet pressures, the pressure transducers are used and set in flooding unit. All samples are collected using the plastic containers for treatment process, and graduated glass tubes for drainage and imbibition processes. All materials and equipment, that have been in the coreflood experiments, are shown in the Figure 2.

In each experiment, the core is put inside Hassler core holder, and Saudi formation water is then injected inside the sandstone core to find the absolute permeability of the core regarding to Darcy's Law. The ammonium chloride solution is then injected to try removing any chemical elements such as sodium potassium and magnesium that can cause any precipitations. When the pressure difference is constant and stable, the pre-treatment permeability can be calculated. To be more realistic, the damage can be created by injecting one pore volume of drilling mud inside core, the permeability can be found, and this is called damaged permeability. After that, the main treatment is applied by injecting the organic mud acid mixture till the pressure is stable, and this is called treated permeability. The ammonium

Figure 2: Schematic of Coreflood Unit

chloride solution is then injected at 5 cc/min to remove the remaining organic mud acid from the porous media, and the post-treatment permeability is then determined. At the final procedure of the treatment process, toluene is injected to clean the porous media from any impurities, and the SFW is then injected the same direction of treatment direction till the injection pressure no change. Finally, the drainage and imbibition processes are done in the reverse direction of treatment direction to examine the permeabilities of both processes as well as the recovery enhancements if it is occurred. Furthermore, after finalizing coreflood tests, all cores are cleaned, dried and saturated with SFW to find its dry and saturated weights to calculate their porosities that are called post-porosities.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Four experiments have been employed to investigate the acidizing of sandstone cores from different angles and views. All Porosities of pre- and post- treatments for both fractured and unfractured cores

are obtained as listed in the Table 1. All values in Table 1 are reasonable values, and Core (A) and Core (B) have almost porosity enhancements with 13% and 21% of original porosity respectively. On the other hand, the total porosity after Core (C) treatment does not computed due to several reasons that will be mentioned later with more details. However, it has higher porosity value rather than other cores since it has fracture or channel with 45 degree angle approximately.

Table 1: Pre- and Post-Treatments Properties of Homogeneous and Fractured Berea Sandstone Cores.

	Length,	Frac.	V_{Bulk},	V_{Pore},	Phi	Phi
	cm	Length, cm	cc	cc	Pre_Tre,%	Post_Tre,%
Core A	9.2	0	104.83	20.24	19.31	21.74
Core B	9.2	0	104.83	19.02	18.20	22.0
Core C	9.2	15.71	104.83	22.04	19.73	Mistreatment

The permeabilities of SWF, NH₄Cl and drilling mud injections inside Core (A) have been experimentally measured and computed, its values are 80 mD, 108 mD and 28 mD respectively as indicated in the Figure 3. To prevent any precipitations, five pore volumes of ammonium chloride solution after SFW are injected in the main treatment, and this comment agrees with Yang et al. (2012).

For Core (C), its SWF, NH₄Cl and drilling mud permeabilities are 176 mD, 235 mD and 55 mD respectively, and these values clear that the increase in permeability in Core (C) is due to the channel and fracture that have on it. Core (B) does not have damage scenario, and its SFW and ammonium chloride solution permeabilities are 87 mD and 118 mD. As described in Equation (1), the ammonium chloride and water can be chemically reaction, and its reaction results hydrochloric acid. All bars in Figure 3 show that the fractured sandstone has highest permeability rather than other cores which are damaged and undamaged cores. In addition, permeabilities of homogenous sandstone cores are similar.

Figure 3: Permeability Measurements of Homogeneous and Fractured Berea Sandstone Cores using Saudi Formation Water, Ammonium Chloride and Drilling Mud at 1000 psi and 140 °F.

The target of stimulation process especially on acidizing process returns the permeability to the original permeability “100%” or permeability enhancement “more than 100%”. As indicated in the main treatment stage in Figure 4, the permeability treatment factor “PTF” slightly decreases to 88% of original permeability. Due to the reactions between the organic mud acid and quartz and clays, the minerals precipitate and then plug channels. Therefore, the permeability enhancement does not occur, and this observation agrees with the published results. Post-treatment using ammonium chloride is then injected at high flow rate to clean the porous media from any precipitations and remove remaining amount of acids to eliminate any additional reactions that can lead to damage the core sample. In the post-treatment stage, the PTF seems that the injection of 2.5 pore volumes of ammonium chloride solution is sufficient to treat 136% of original permeability. The PTF of core (A) decreases 25% of original permeability when drilling mud is injected inside it as shown in Figure 5. It is cleared

Figure 4: Permeability Profile of Homogenous Berea Sandstone Core without Damaging during Main Treatment and Post-Flush Stages at 1000 Psi and 140 °F. “Experiment Two” “Core (B)”

that the organic mud acid, which is called a main treatment stage, can try to return core (A) permeability to original value “100%”, unfortunately, the PTF reaches to 92% of original permeability. This treatment occurs due to the successful reaction between hydrofluoric acid and clays, and acetic acid and ammonium chloride can be accelerate and regulate the solubility process inside the core at high pressure and temperature as indicated in Equations (1) and (2). On the other side, the improvement of permeability is obviously rapid when the ammonium chloride solution is injected, and its PTF is about 136% of original permeability. This enhancement can be resulted from the removing all reaction products that be precipitated from the main treatment stage since the injection of this fluid is under high injection rate comparing with others injection stages. In both Figures 4 and 5, the PTFs for both cores are almost similar, and their PFTs are around 136% of original permeability. However, the big differences between them are occurred in the mechanism of treatment processes as shown in Figures 4 and 5. In the homogenous sandstone core with damaging

Figure 5: Permeability Profile of Homogeneous Berea Sandstone Core with Damaging using Drilling Mud during Main Treatment and Post-Flush Stages at 1000 Psi and 140 °F. “Experiment One” “Core (A)”

process, the organic mud acid can increase the permeability of the core since the organic mud acid mixes with ammonium chloride solution, and those can increase the possibility of dissolving clays using hydrofluoric acid and solubility of any minerals that can react with acetic acid as well as ammonium chloride solution. On the other hand, the permeability reduction can be happened in homogeneous sandstone core without damaging in order to increase the precipitations of core minerals and plug the pores and channels inside core, consequently, the permeability trend in the main treatment stage is fluctuation. In post treatment stage in both cores, the injection of ammonium chloride solution in homogeneous sandstone core without damaging process is around 2.5 pore volumes to reach the optimum permeability enhancement and treatment, and this result agrees with published results. On the contrary, the amount of ammonium chloride solution injection in the post treatment stage in homogeneous sandstone core with damaging process is approximately 1.5 pore volumes injection, however, this case is consumed around 9 pore volumes of organic mud acid so it is costly comparing with previous case.

The Figure 6 is shown the treatment behaviour inside the fractured sandstone core, and the permeability treatment factor decreases from 25% to 15% of original permeability at the beginning of organic mud acid injection. This is referred to increase the possibility of plugging the fractured or channel regarding to use the drilling mud, in addition, fines could migrate through the channel without any restrictions. The improvement in permeability especially on main treatment stage is slowly occurred as indicated in Figure 6, and the PTF increases from 15% till 42% of original permeability of core (C) at five pore volumes of organic mud acid injection. In the post-treatment stage, the PTF is however increased from the 42% till 68% of original permeability, hence, the permeability enhancement in fractured sandstone core has not been achievable and successful. Because it has not returned to the original permeability which has high permeability, and this result is logical and it can agree with published result (McCune et al., 1975). The major phenomena is visually observed in the fractured sandstone core that drilling mud cannot remove in both main treatment and post treatment stages, since organic mud acid and ammonium chloride

bypass the drilling mud where is located around fracture on the sandstone core. Hence, the treatment in fractured sandstone core using organic mud acid cannot be successful as shown in the Figure 7. For comparisons between all values of permeabilities in whole treatment stages, the mud drilling permeabilities in all cores have the minimum values as shown in the Figure 8. The highest permeability value is in fractured sandstone core, unfortunately, the permeability after treatment process has not enhancement. On the other hand, the permeabilities after whole treatment stages in homogeneous sandstone cores are improved with same enhancement percentages.

Figure 6: Permeability Profile of Fractured Berea Sandstone Core with Damaging using Drilling Mud during Main Treatment and Post-Flush Stages at 1000 Psi and 140 °F. "Experiment Three" "Core (C)"

Figure 7: The Visual Observations on Homogeneous and Fractured Berea Sandstone Cores after Treatment Processes: (a) Side Views and (b) Injection Faces of all Acidizing Stages. “Core (A, C)”

Figure 8: Permeabilities of Homogeneous and Fractured Berea Sandstone Cores for Pre-Flush, Damaging, Main Treatment and Post-Flush Stages using Different Fluid at 1000 psi and 140 °F.

After acidizing and treatment processes, all treated cores are cleaned and prepared them to apply both drainage and imbibition processes in the same treated cores, but the oil and water floods in the reverse direction of the acidizing direction to mimic the acidizing job in the field. This part is a crucial part to

address the effect of permeability treatment of sandstone samples on oil recovery factor as shown in Figure 9. The oil recovery of the original core is 40% of Original Oil in Place “OOIP” as indicated in the result of experiment four in the Figure 9. The improvement percentages of damaged and undamaged sandstone cores are almost similar 136%, and its recoveries are respectively 65% and 66% of OOIP. For fractured sandstone core, its treatment has not achieved in order to bypass the treatment fluid through the channel, however, it has still reasonable recovery comparing with other cores, and its value is 56% of OOIP.

Figure 9: Recovery Factor and Ratio between Post- and Pre- Permeabilities for Different Berea Sandstone Cores at 1000 Psi and 140 °F.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In this paper, it has been suggested and implemented the new treatment system as one-step treatment without using hydrochloric acid as pre- and post- flush stages due to several reasons that can minimize the treatment difficulties and issues as well as treatment time. Based on chemical reactions between ammonium chloride, water and acetic acid and other solutions, hydrochloric acid can be found by chemical reaction. The organic mud acid, which is composed 2wt% hydrofluoric acid and 15wt% acetic acid and mix them with 5wt% ammonium chloride, can be provided the successful treatment and acidizing process in homogeneous sandstone formation. On the other side, the treatment of fractured damaged sandstone cannot return to the original permeability. Finally, the oil recovery of tread homogeneous cores produces more oil rather than the core which has not treatment process.

It is recommended to study the effect of various parameters on acidizing job using organic mud acid in both homogeneous and fractured sandstone cores experimentally, and these parameters can be temperature, pressure, injection rate and fracture orientations as well as length.

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